

Genomic Analyses

Phylogenetic Analyses

Preliminary Screening

De novo Assembly

Identifying Gap Bridging Reads

Genomic location of pPCP1 insertion

Maximum Likelihood Phylogeny

- ① Samples downloaded from online repositories & selected from Institut Pasteur collection.
- ② Samples mapped to *Yersinia pestis* CO92 reference sequence.
- ③ Average depth of pPCP1, *pst* and *pla* calculated.
- ④ Linear regression and histograms of *pst*/*pla* ratios in samples with >10X pPCP1 coverage.
- ⑤ Presence/absence analysis of all protein coding genes performed.

- ⑥ pPCP1 specific enrichment of aDNA.
- ⑦ *de novo* assembly of pPCP1^{Δ*pla*} from G861x1035 & pPCP1^{WT} from G25Bx98.
- ⑧ Long read sequence analysis of Vietnamese isolates, revealing pPCP1 insertion into pCD1.

- ⑨ Competitive mapping to CO92 and pPCP1^{Δ*pla*}. Gap bridging reads identified.
- ⑩ Samples identified as wildtype or *pla*-reduced.

- ⑪ *de novo* assembly of pPCP1-pCD1 attempted from Gdansk8.
- ⑫ Gargammel used to simulate aDNA library containing pPCP1-pCD1, for *de novo* assembly.
- ⑬ Depth analysis of illumina data from Vietnamese isolates revealed equivalent depths between *pla* and pCD1.
- ⑭ Sample G861x1035 deeply shotgun sequenced to determine location of pPCP1 insertion in ancient strains. Additional ancient samples with shotgun data also included in depth comparison (G488, G701, and X52).

- ⑮ Pairwise alignment of ancient and modern *Y. pestis* genomes to CO92, requiring SNPs to be present at a frequency of 3X and 0.9, using snippy. Followed by multiple alignment of output with snippy-core.
- ⑯ Chromosomal SNPs extracted and filtered for sites with coverage in 95% of samples. Singleton SNPs retained.
- ⑰ Full Maximum Likelihood Tree reconstructed and subtrees extracted.

in vitro analyses

in vivo analyses

Plasminogen Activation Assay

Bubonic infection assay

Pneumonic infection assay

Septicemic infection assay

- ⑱ *in-vitro* plasminogen assay on *pla*-wildtype, *pla*-reduced, and *pla*-intermediate strains.
- ⑲ Individual colonies from 'mixed' phenotypes sequenced, to ascertain genotypes.

- ⑳ Survival analysis after subcutaneous or intradermal injection with wildtype, *pla*-intermediate, *pla*-reduced, and *pla*-inactivated *Y. pestis* strains.

- ㉑ Survival analysis after intranasal inoculation with wildtype, *pla*-reduced, and *pla*-inactivated *Y. pestis* strains.

- ㉒ Survival analysis after intravenous injection with wildtype, *pla*-reduced, and *pla*-inactivated *Y. pestis* strains.